

Supporting Information for

A-site cation engineering in two-
dimensional Ruddlesden-Popper
 $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films

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Figure S1. A) Experimental thin film (red line) and simulated (blue line) X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite. B) Absorption spectrum of a $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite film.

Figure S2. Normalized X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Rb}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (B), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Cs}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (C) and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{FA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (D) 2D RP perovskite films.

Figure S4. 2D GIWAXS patterns of the mixed A-cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ with 60% Gua (A), 100% Gua (B), 50% DA (C), 60% EA (D), 90% EA (E), 20% Rb (F), 30% Rb (G), 20% PA (H), 30% PA (I), 20% Cs (J) and 30% Cs (K) perovskite films.

Figure S5. Top-surface SEM images of the mixed A-cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 60% of Gua (A), 100% of Gua (B), 60% of EA (C), 90% of EA (D), 30% of Cs (E), 30% of Rb (F), 50% of DA (G) and 30% of PA (H). Scale bar, 2 μm .

Figure S6. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S7. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{Gua}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S8. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.4}\text{Gua}_{0.6})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S9. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{Gua})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S10. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{EA}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S11. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.4}\text{EA}_{0.6})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S12. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.1}\text{EA}_{0.9})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S13. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{Cs}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_{31}\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S14. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.7}\text{Cs}_{0.3})_2\text{Pb}_{31}\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S15. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{Rb}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_{31}\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S16. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.7}\text{Rb}_{0.3})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S17. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{DA}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S18. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.5}\text{DA}_{0.5})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S19. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{PA}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Figure S20. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{0.7}\text{PA}_{0.3})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Table S1. Atomic percentages of C, Pb and I obtained from EDX analysis of the different mixed cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films.

Cation	%	C (Atomic %)	Pb (Atomic %)	I (Atomic %)
Reference		54.34	7.38	23.42
Gua	20	49.28	8.16	25.87
	60	48.91	7.63	21.75
	100	51.90	7.82	24.86
EA	20	51.59	7.65	23.80
	60	54.01	6.87	21.13
	90	55.37	7.19	22.63
Cs	20	53.05	7.16	22.76
	30	49.46	7.90	24.41
Rb	20	52.64	8.03	24.92
	30	52.28	8.24	22.80
DA	20	52.35	7.55	23.53
	50	56.68	6.79	20.29
PA	20	49.39	6.55	21.06
	30	54.50	6.96	21.93

Figure S21. Absorption spectra of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$, (A) $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Rb}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (B) and (C), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Cs}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (D) and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{FA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (E) 2D RP perovskite films.

Figure S22. Changes in the absorption intensity at 610 nm ($n = 3$) at increasing percentages of the A-cation with EA (A), Gua (B), DA (C), PA (D), Rb (E) and Cs (F).

Figure S23. Normalized photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the mixed A-cation $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$, (A) $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Rb}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (B), $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Cs}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (C) and $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{FA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (D) 2D RP perovskite films.

Table S2. Photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) of the mixed A-cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite films at the different percentage of the A-cation.

	% A-cation in the $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite										
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
DA	0.26	0.13	0.15	0.05	0.14	0.07	0.26	0.22	0.16	0.15	0.50
Cs	0.26	0.20	0.11	0.09	0.07	0.03	0.009	0.004	0.005	0.005	0.005
Gua	0.26	0.45	0.40	0.27	0.22	0.27	0.08	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.07
EA	0.26	0.28	0.30	0.24	0.31	0.23	0.19	0.20	0.24	0.04	0.03
Rb	0.26	0.26	0.29	0.30	0.27	0.20	0.15	0.37	0.32	0.41	0.50
PA	0.26	0.25	0.26	0.30	0.40	0.29	0.28	0.07	0.06	0.009	0.007

Figure S24. Time-resolved PL signal at the maximum of each PL peak of $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Rb}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A), $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PA}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ and $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Cs}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite films with different PA, Rb and Cs contents. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$.

Table S3. Time constant (τ) and weighting factors (a) of the PL decays obtained after exponential fit of the experimental data for all mixed A-cation $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{A}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ 2D RP perovskite films at the different percentage of the A-cation.

Cation	%	τ_1	a_1	τ_2	a_2	τ_3	a_3	τ_{av}
EA	0	0.29	0.35	1.7	0.50	9.6	0.15	2.4
	10	0.28	0.35	1.6	0.52	7.6	0.13	1.9
	20	0.29	0.25	1.6	0.45	6.3	0.30	2.7
	30	0.31	0.26	1.6	0.46	6.8	0.28	2.7
	40	0.22	0.30	1.2	0.41	5.9	0.29	2.3
	50	0.15	0.34	0.8	0.44	3.6	0.22	1.2
	60	0.14	0.40	0.7	0.41	3.4	0.19	1.0
	70	0.14	0.40	0.9	0.40	6.0	0.20	1.6
	80	0.13	0.38	0.7	0.42	2.7	0.20	0.9
	90	0.11	0.48	0.8	0.34	5.3	0.18	1.3
Gua	100	0.06	0.65	0.4	0.25	3.1	0.10	0.5
	10	0.30	0.19	3.2	0.40	12	0.41	6.3
	20	0.28	0.20	3.3	0.51	10.5	0.29	4.8
	30	0.31	0.44	2.4	0.43	18	0.14	3.5
	50	0.18	0.61	1.1	0.39			0.6
	80	0.20	0.67	1.3	0.33			0.6
DA	100	0.06	0.85	0.6	0.15			0.1
	10	0.21	0.29	1.2	0.46	6.3	0.25	2.1
	20	0.16	0.45	0.9	0.40	5.6	0.15	1.3
	30	0.17	0.41	0.9	0.41	4.9	0.18	1.3
	40	0.16	0.43	1.0	0.39	6.5	0.18	1.7
	50	0.12	0.38	1.2	0.29	7.9	0.33	3.0
	60	0.15	0.42	1.0	0.34	7.6	0.24	2.2
	70	0.16	0.36	1.0	0.41	8.3	0.23	2.4
	80	0.14	0.25	1.2	0.39	9.9	0.36	4.0
	90	0.09	0.39	0.9	0.35	8.1	0.25	2.4
PA	100	0.06	0.83	0.4	0.17			0.1
	10	0.14	0.36	0.9	0.39	4.9	0.25	1.6
	20	0.16	0.41	0.8	0.40	3.6	0.19	1.1
	30	0.11	0.46	0.5	0.36	2.2	0.18	0.6

	40	0.10	0.43	0.4	0.39	1.7	0.18	0.5
	50	0.12	0.48	0.6	0.36	2.9	0.16	0.7
	60	0.09	0.56	0.5	0.32	2.4	0.12	0.5
	70	0.10	0.50	0.6	0.35	3.7	0.15	0.8
Rb	10	0.49	0.31	3.0	0.53	15	0.16	4.1
	25	0.28	0.26	1.5	0.48	7.2	0.26	2.6
	50	0.13	0.46	0.5	0.44	1.7	0.10	0.5
	70	0.18	0.42	0.6	0.48	1.9	0.10	0.6
	90	0.09	0.44	0.4	0.42	1.5	0.14	0.4
Cs	100	0.07	0.78	0.2	0.22			0.1
	10	0.23	0.26	1.2	0.59	4.9	0.15	1.5
	20	0.20	0.44	0.8	0.48	4.2	0.08	0.8
	30	0.20	0.62	0.9	0.25	5.5	0.13	1.0
	40	0.11	0.54	0.6	0.31	3.8	0.15	0.8
	50	0.11	0.51	0.7	0.31	4.0	0.18	1.0
	70	0.14	0.43	0.8	0.38	3.9	0.19	1.1
100	0.11	0.50	0.7	0.25	7.8	0.25	2.2	

Figure S25. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times (A, B, C, D and E) and time decays at $\lambda_{\text{probe}} \approx 572 \text{ nm}$, 607 nm , 640 nm and 750 nm (F, G, H, I and J) of the $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{A}_{0.2})_2\text{Pb}_{310}$ perovskite films with Gua (A and F), DA (B and G), Rb (C and H), PA (D and I) and Cs (E and J). $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S26. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times (A, B and C) and time decays at $\lambda_{\text{probe}} \approx 572 \text{ nm}$, 607 nm , 640 nm and 690 nm (D, E and F) of the $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.7}\text{A}_{0.3})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with Rb (A and D), PA (B and E) and Cs (C and F). $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S27. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times (A and B) and time decays at $\lambda_{\text{probe}} \approx 572 \text{ nm}$, 607 nm , 640 nm and 690 nm (C and D) of the $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.4}\text{Gua}_{0.6})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (A and C) and $\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.5}\text{DA}_{0.5})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$.

The Goldschmidt tolerance factor in perovskites with a non-spherical central cation

The tolerance factor calculated for three dimensional perovskites allows one to predict the stability of the material by using the effective ionic radii of the ions forming the perovskite. Thus, the 3D APbI_3 perovskites are stable when their tolerance factors are in the range of $0.8 < t < 1$, as it occurs when A is the methylammonium cation (MA). However, if the tolerance factor is larger than 1, as it happens with the guanidinium (Gua) or the ethylammonium (EA) cation, the 3D perovskites are not formed due to the low stability of the inorganic network. However, there is a piece of experimental evidence showing that the EA and the Gua cations can be partially incorporated into the inorganic network by replacement of the MA cation, forming 3D structures with a composition of $\text{MA}_{(1-x)}\text{A}_x\text{PbI}_3$, with x_A being the fraction of the A cation, 0.3-0.4 for the EA¹ cation and 0.25 for the Gua cation.² Likewise, it has been observed that the Gua, EA and DA cations can form 2D Ruddlesden Popper perovskites with $n = 2$,³⁻⁵ and even with $n = 3$ for the EA cation.⁶⁻⁷ To explain the formation of the mixed A-cation perovskites, a redefinition of the tolerance factor will be carried using simple geometric criteria.

Figure S28. A) Crystal structure of the 3D ABX_3 perovskite showing the geometric parameters that define the Goldschmidt tolerance factor. B) Sketch of the octahedral cage filled with the Gua cation and showing the three perpendicular planes.

Figure S28A shows the structure of a cubic ABX_3 perovskite with a spherical A cation localized at the center of the octahedral cage. A section plane is also shown including the distances among the atoms. Based on the relationship between effective ionic radii indicated in Figure S28A, it is possible to define the Goldschmidt tolerance factor as:

$$t = \frac{(r_A + r_x)}{\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_x)} < 1 \quad (1)$$

In case of the MA cation, with radius $r_{MA} = 2.17\text{\AA}$,⁸ it behaves in practice as a spherical cation, at least in the temperature range of 140-370 K, because it experiences rotational movements around its different axes inside the octahedral cavity.⁹ In case of the Gua or EA cations, we hypothesize that they do not undergo such rotational movements due to their larger size. Thus, it is experimentally observed that the rotational movements of the Gua cation are sterically prohibited in the cage.³

In a cubic 3D perovskite, it is possible to define three identical planes as those shown in Figure S28A due to the 12 iodine atoms that coordinate the central ion. Each of these planes is delimited by 4 iodine atoms which form a perfect square. When an anisotropic cation is inserted into the cage, the cubic symmetry is lost. Furthermore, the specific geometry of the cation induces rotation and/or deformation of the surrounding octahedra to accommodate the new cation inside the cavity. In this situation, the three previous planes are no identical, which suggests the possibility of defining three tolerance factors, one for each of these planes (see Figure S28B-D). These planes labelled as P_{xy} , P_{xz} and P_{yz} are delimited by 4 iodine atoms that can define an irregular rectangle. The central cation displays different effective ionic radii for each of these planes due to its geometry and spatial orientation.

To simplify the following treatment as much as possible and simultaneously show an example of its applicability, we will assume the cubic structure of the $MAPbI_3$ perovskite where the MA is replaced by the A cation, with a larger size than MA. In the following, the A cation will be represented by the Gua cation (see Figure S29A). We will assume that the distance Pb-I is $b = (r_{Pb} + r_I) = 3.2\text{\AA}$, and that the iodine ionic radius is $r_I = 2.2\text{\AA}$. With these values and assuming a cubic structure in which the tolerance factor is $t = 1$, it can be obtained from equation (1), that $r_A = b\sqrt{2} - r_I = 2.325\text{\AA}$. Therefore, cations with ionic radii less than this value would not disturb the cubic network and could be mixed in any proportion with MA, but cations with ionic radii greater than the previous value would need to distort the cubic network to be inserted into the cage (see Figure S29A and S29B).

We will first analyze the distortions caused by the not spherical central cation, A, in the cavity. We will assume that the longest axis of the ion is oriented along the z axis. As indicated above, we will use the Gua cation assuming that the plane of the Gua cation is in the x-z plane of the reference system. We will name r_{xz} as the radius of the A cation in the P_{xz} plane, whose value is $r_{xz} > 2.325\text{\AA}$. Thus, in the case of the Gua cation $r_{xz}(Gua) = 2.78\text{\AA}$.⁸ We assume that the cage is going to be disturbed only along the

plane in which the cation is situated, the P_{xz} plane, which must be expanded to allow the incorporation of the cation. In this way, we neglect the distortions on the other two planes (P_{xy} and P_{yz}) since the ionic radii in those planes, r_{xy} and r_{yz} , are less than 2.325 Å.

Figure S29. A) Crystal network of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite where a MA cation has been replaced by a Gua cation producing a distortion in the Pb-I-Pb angle (θ). B) Close view of the distortion of the Pb-I-Pb angle by the Gua cation and the P_{xz} plane that includes the plane of the Gua cation. C) Sketch of the triangle that defines the distances for the calculation of the Goldschmidt tolerance factor.

The expansion of the P_{xz} plane can take place through various mechanisms: increase of the Pb-I distance along the x or z axes, rotation of the involved octahedra and/or folding the Pb-I-Pb bond angle along the y axis. To simplify our treatment, we will assume that the Pb-I distances along the x and z axes are kept constant and equal to $b = (r_{Pb} + r_I) = 3.2$ Å, and that the deformation of the cavity takes place exclusively by folding the Pb-I-Pb bond angle along the y axis (θ angle, see Figure S29). Furthermore, due to this folding, it will be assumed that the iodine atoms of the Pb-I-Pb bond move along the z axis, towards the external side of the cavity (see red arrows in Figure S29A). Thus, the Pb-I distance along the y axis increases up to a value of $b/\sin(\theta/2)$ (see Figure S29B).

Now, we look at the P_{xz} plane (Figures S29B and S29C) which is delimited by 4 iodine atoms that make up a rectangle (Figure S29C). The tolerance factor on the x-z plane can be established from the right triangle drawn in figure S29C, so that in an ideal case:

$$(r_{xz} + r_I)^2 = b^2 + b^2 \left(1 + \frac{\cos(\theta/2)}{\sin(\theta/2)}\right)^2 = (r_{Pb} + r_I)^2 \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{\cos(\theta/2)}{\sin(\theta/2)}\right)^2\right] \quad (2)$$

Allowing to define the tolerance factor in this x-z plane as:

$$t_A(xz) = \frac{(r_{xz} + r_I)}{(r_{Pb} + r_I) \sqrt{1 + \left(1 + \frac{\cos(\theta/2)}{\sin(\theta/2)}\right)^2}} \quad (3)$$

The expansion of the P_{xz} plane in the cavity where the voluminous A cation is located must be at the expense of the contraction of this plane in the adjacent cages, where the MA ion is located. Thus, it is necessary to define an additional tolerance factor for the MA cation. The inclusion of the bulky cation will be only possible if the tolerance factor of the MA cation in the adjacent cage is less than the unity. If the cation introduced into the network is not very voluminous, the distortion can be assumed by the neighboring cavities, however, if the A cation is very voluminous, the distortion can affect more distant regions of the network.

Figure S30. A) Crystal structure of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite where $\frac{1}{2}$ of the MA cations are replaced by Gua cations. B) Close view of the adjacent cages containing MA and Gua cations showing the distortions in the network and the distances among atoms as a function of the Pb-I-Pb bond angles (θ).

To analyze the contraction of the cavity occupied by the MA cations, we assume the formation of a mixed A-cation perovskite with composition $MA_{(1-x)}A_xPbI_3$, analyzing three possible situations, corresponding to $x_A = 1/2$, $1/3$ and $1/4$. Figure S30A shows the structure at $x_A = 1/2$, where the A cation is represented by Gua. In this structure, the MA and A cations are alternated in adjacent cavities.

The distortion caused by the A cation in its cavity is represented by equation 3. If we now look at the cavity occupied by the MA cation, the size of the P_{xz} plane decreases to the same extent to the increase of the same plane in the cavity occupied by the A cation. The tolerance factor of the MA cation in this plane can be defined equivalently to how it was done before in the case of the A cation (the exponent of t indicates the mole fraction of MA, $x_{MA} = 1/2$):

$$t_{MA}^{1/2}(xz) = \frac{(r_{MA}+r_I)}{(r_{Pb}+r_I) \sqrt{1+\left(1-\frac{\cos(\theta/2)}{\sin(\theta/2)}\right)^2}} = \frac{S_{MA}}{\sqrt{1+(1-x)^2}} \quad (4)$$

$$S_{MA} = \frac{r_{MA}+r_I}{r_{Pb}+r_I} \quad x = \frac{\cos(\theta/2)}{\sin(\theta/2)}$$

The previous equation agrees well with the general definition of the tolerance factor when $\theta = 180^\circ$, but unlike in the equation (3) for the Gua cation, $t_{MA}^{1/2}(xz)$ increases as the θ angle decreases. If we now fix $t_{MA}^{1/2}(xz) = 1$ and solve equation (4) for x , then it is possible to express $t_A^{1/2}(xz)$ as a function of only S_A and S_{MA} .

$$t_A^{1/2}(xz) = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+(1+x)^2}} = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+\left(2-\sqrt{S_{MA}^2-1}\right)^2}}$$

$$S_A = \frac{r_A + r_I}{r_{Pb} + r_I}$$

It is now supposed that $x_A = 1/3$. In Figure S31A, the structure of the 3D $MAPbI_3$ is shown where $1/3$ of the MA cations are replaced by the A cation (Gua). Unlike the previous case, the presence of the A cation only distorts one of the planes of the adjacent cavities where the MA is located (see Figure S31B). The tolerance factor of the MA cation can be expressed as:

$$t_{MA}^{2/3}(xz) = \frac{(r_{MA}+r_I)}{(r_{Pb}+r_I) \sqrt{1+\left(1-\frac{\cos(\theta/2)}{2\sin(\theta/2)}\right)^2}} = \frac{S_{MA}}{\sqrt{1+\left(1-\frac{x}{2}\right)^2}} \quad (5)$$

If we now fix $t_{MA}^{2/3}(xz) = 1$ and solve equation (5) for x , then it is possible to express $t_A^{2/3}(xz)$ as a function of only S_A and S_{MA} .

$$t_A^{2/3}(xz) = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+(1+x)^2}} = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+\left(3-2\cdot\sqrt{S_{MA}^2-1}\right)^2}}$$

Figure S31. A) Crystal structure of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite where 1/3 of the MA cations are replaced by Gua cations. B) Close view of the adjacent cages containing MA and Gua cations showing the distortions in the network and the distances among atoms as a function of the Pb-I-Pb bond angles (θ).

It is finally supposed that $x_A = 1/4$, i.e., 1/4 of the MA cations are replaced by the A cation (Gua in Figure S32A). In this case, we will assume that the A cation has a size such that $r_{xz} > 2.655 \text{ \AA}$ and that the distortions in the network cannot be counteracted by only the adjacent cavity occupied by the MA cation. Therefore, to allow the bulky cation to be incorporated into the cage, we assume that the distortions affect not only to the adjacent cavity but to the following ones. This is reflected in the structure proposed

in Figure S32A. Thus, two different locations can be defined for the MA cations. First, the cavities adjacent to those where the A cation is situated, which are called MA₁, and secondly, the cavities non-adjacent to those in which the A cation is located, which are called MA₂. An adjacent cavity is always along the z axis, where the distortion occurs.

Figure S32. A) Crystal structure of the 3D MAPbI₃ perovskite where 1/4 of the MA cations are replaced by Gua cations. B) Close view of the adjacent cages containing MA and Gua cations showing the distortions in the network and the distances among atoms as a function of the Pb-I-Pb bond angles (θ).

The cavity in which the MA₁ cations are located presents an asymmetric deformation. On one hand, in the side adjacent to the A cation, the folding of the Pb-I-Pb angle has a value of θ_1 , which coincides with that taking place in the cavity occupied by the A cation. This folding reduces the surface of the P_{xz} plane inside the cavity where the MA₁ cation is located. On the other hand, in the side of the cavity parallel to the previous one, the folding takes the θ_2 value, and this folding increases the surface of the P_{xz} plane. The tolerance factor of these MA₁ cations will be (see Figure S32B):

$$t_{MA}^{3/4}(xz) = \frac{(r_{xz} + r_I)}{(r_{Pb} + r_I) \sqrt{1 + \left(1 - \frac{\cos(\theta_1/2)}{2\sin(\theta_1/2)} + \frac{\cos(\theta_2/2)}{2\sin(\theta_2/2)}\right)^2}} = \frac{S_{MA}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(1 - \frac{x}{2} + \frac{x\theta}{2}\right)^2}} \quad (6)$$

$$x_o = 1 - \sqrt{S_{MA}^2 - 1}$$

The cavity in which the MA₂ cations are located presents a symmetrical deformation, being θ_2 the Pb-I-Pb bond angle, which implies the reduction of the surface of the P_{xz} plane inside the cavity (see Figure S32B). The tolerance factor is given by an equation identical to equation (4). Remember that, according to equation (4), the tolerance factor is less than or equal to one if $\theta \geq 172^\circ$. Therefore, the minimum allowed value for θ_2 is 172° .

If we now fix $t_{MA}^{3/4}(xz) = 1$ and solve equation (6) for x , then it is possible to express $t_A^{3/4}(xz)$ as a function of only S_A and S_{MA} .

$$t_A^{3/4}(xz) = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+(1+x)^2}} = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+\left(4-3\cdot\sqrt{S_{MA}^2-1}\right)^2}}$$

This result can be generalized for a mixed A-cation perovskite with composition x_A following the next equation:

$$t_A(xz) = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+\left[1+\frac{(1-x_A)}{x_A}\left(1-\sqrt{S_{MA}^2-1}\right)\right]^2}} = \frac{S_A}{\sqrt{1+\left[\frac{1-(1-x_A)\sqrt{S_{MA}^2-1}}{x_A}\right]^2}}$$

Figure 33. J-V curve of the champion solar cells prepared with the mixed cation BA₂(MA_{1-x}A_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskites with 5% PA (A), 5% Rb (B) and 10% Cs (C) A-cation.

References

- (1) Wang, Y.; Zhang, T.; Li, G.; Xu, F.; Wang, T.; Li, Y.; Yang, Y.; Zhao, Y. A Mixed-Cation Lead Iodide $MA_{1-x}EA_xPbI_3$ Absorber for Perovskite Solar Cells. *J. Energy Chem.* **2018**, *27* (1), 215–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2017.09.027>.
- (2) Jodlowski, A. D.; Roldán-Carmona, C.; Grancini, G.; Salado, M.; Ralaiarisoa, M.; Ahmad, S.; Koch, N.; Camacho, L.; De Miguel, G.; Nazeeruddin, M. K. Large Guanidinium Cation Mixed with Methylammonium in Lead Iodide Perovskites for 19% Efficient Solar Cells. *Nat. Energy* **2017**, *2* (12), 972–979. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-017-0054-3>.
- (3) Fu, Y.; Hautzinger, M. P.; Luo, Z.; Wang, F.; Pan, D.; Aristov, M. M.; Guzei, I. A.; Pan, A.; Zhu, X.; Jin, S. Incorporating Large A Cations into Lead Iodide Perovskite Cages: Relaxed Goldschmidt Tolerance Factor and Impact on Exciton-Phonon Interaction. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2019**, *5* (8), 1377–1386. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.9b00367>.
- (4) Li, X.; Fu, Y.; Pedesseau, L.; Guo, P.; Cuthriell, S.; Hadar, I.; Even, J.; Katan, C.; Stoumpos, C. C.; Schaller, R. D.; Harel, E.; Kanatzidis, M. G. Negative Pressure Engineering with Large Cage Cations in 2D Halide Perovskites Causes Lattice Softening. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142* (26), 11486–11496. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.0c03860>.
- (5) Hautzinger, M. P.; Pan, D.; Pigg, A. K.; Fu, Y.; Morrow, D. J.; Leng, M.; Kuo, M.-Y.; Spitha, N.; Lafayette, D. P.; Kohler, D. D.; Wright, J. C.; Jin, S. Band Edge Tuning of Two-Dimensional Ruddlesden–Popper Perovskites by A Cation Size Revealed through Nanoplates. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2020**, *5* (5), 1430–1437. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenerylett.0c00450>.
- (6) Fu, Y.; Jiang, X.; Li, X.; Traore, B.; Spanopoulos, I.; Katan, C.; Even, J.; Kanatzidis, M. G.; Harel, E. Cation Engineering in Two-Dimensional Ruddlesden–Popper Lead Iodide Perovskites with Mixed Large A-Site Cations in the Cages. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142* (8), 4008–4021. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.9b13587>.
- (7) Liang, M.; Lin, W.; Lan, Z.; Meng, J.; Zhao, Q.; Zou, X.; Castelli, I. E.; Pullerits, T.; Canton, S. E.; Zheng, K. Electronic Structure and Trap States of Two-Dimensional Ruddlesden–Popper Perovskites with the Relaxed Goldschmidt Tolerance Factor. *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.* **2020**, *2* (5), 1402–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaelm.0c00179>.
- (8) Kieslich, G.; Sun, S.; Cheetham, A. K. Solid-State Principles Applied to Organic–Inorganic Perovskites: New Tricks for an Old Dog. *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, *5* (12), 4712–4715. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4sc02211d>.
- (9) Leguy, A. M. A.; Frost, J. M.; McMahon, A. P.; Sakai, V. G.; Kochemann, W.; Law, C.; Li, X.; Foglia, F.; Walsh, A.; O'Regan, B. C.; Nelson, J.;

Cabral, J. T.; Barnes, P. R. F. The Dynamics of Methylammonium Ions in Hybrid Organic-Inorganic Perovskite Solar Cells. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6* (5). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8124>.